

DIELECTRIC CONSTANT AND DIPOLE MOMENT: ETHERS, ALDEHYDES AND CHLORO COMPOUNDS

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The dielectric constants and densities of a number of ethers, pentachloroethane and vanillin have been measured in liquid state and in solution.

The moments are calculated by applying the D.C.M., the Onsager, the Kirkwood and the new equations. The moments of these compounds have also been calculated theoretically. The new moments of the compounds in liquid state and in solution compare well with the vapour values and also with the values calculated theoretically. The moments in the liquid state, as given by the Onsager and Kirkwood equations, are consistently higher.

In the previous paper (*J. Poona Univ.*, 1954) the authors have reported the work on some chloro compounds, aldehydes and ethers. The work is extended further in the present paper.

The dielectric constant and density of β -naphthylmethyl ether have been measured in molten state as well as in benzene solution.

The dielectric constants and densities of tetrahydrofuran, and *o*-, *m*- and *p*-dimethoxybenzenes have been measured at various temperatures. The dielectric constant and density of tetrahydrofuran in benzene have been measured at various concentrations and temperatures.

In all cases, the dipole moments are calculated by applying the new equation and the values obtained are compared with those obtained by the D.C.M., the Onsager and the Kirkwood equations. Also theoretical values are calculated for these substances.

In the case of furan, the data of Smyth and Walls (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 3230) and that of Le Fevre *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1622) have been recalculated by applying the new equation.

The dielectric constant and density of pentachloroethane in liquid state have been measured for the first time, over a range of temperature.

Shott-L'vova and Syrkin (*J. Phys. Chem.*, USSR., 1938, 12, 479) recorded a moment of 3.0 for vanillin in solution. In the present work, the moment of vanillin has been determined in benzene solution at various concentrations and over a range of temperature. The moments of all these compounds have been calculated theoretically by taking into account the induction of bond moments according to the method suggested by the present authors (*J. Poona Univ.*, 1952).

EXPERIMENTAL

Thiophène-free benzene was made by repeatedly washing it with concentrated sulphuric acid, then with alkali and finally with water. It was dried over anhydrous calcium chloride and frozen. The portion which froze at 5.5° was finally distilled over P₂O₅.

Pentachloroethane was distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 158.5° (lit. 159.1°).

β -Naphthylmethyl ether was crystallised from alcohol till the observed m.p. 71° agreed with the literature value (70-72°).

Dimethoxybenzenes (*o*- and *m*-) were purified by distilling under reduced pressure ; *o*-, b.p. 207° (lit. 207°) ; *m*-, b.p. 216° (lit. 217°).

TABLE I*

Phenetole.

f_{λ}	$n_{D, \lambda}$	d_{15}	P_{λ}	μ_{new}
(a). Solvent: benzene at 20°. $P_{\lambda} = 160.9$				
0.00000	2.2825	0.87903	...	...
0.00176	2.287	0.87928	397.7	1.13
0.01827	2.329	0.88129	394.1	1.12
0.03170	2.364	0.88290	391.1	1.11
0.05400	2.421	0.88550	396.3	1.12
0.12193	2.595	0.89280	417.6	1.17
0.46365	3.346	0.92611	406.9	1.15
0.64519	3.684	0.94033	409.1	1.15
0.72488	3.824	0.94619	410.2	1.15
0.90560	4.100	0.95884	409.9	1.15
0.9365	4.141	0.96101	408.8	1.15
0.96994	4.185	0.96336	408.3	1.15
1.00000	4.225	0.96538	408.3	1.15
(b). Solvent: CCl ₄ at 20°.				
0.00000	2.2433	1.5937	...	...
0.00755	2.263	1.5874	423.8	1.19
0.02156	2.298	1.5760	408.3	1.15
0.04931	2.363	1.5535	397.6	1.13
0.23845	2.800	1.4079	400.3	1.13
0.47490	3.306	1.2532	407.0	1.15
0.84180	3.980	1.0439	408.8	1.15
1.00000	4.224	0.9652	408.3	1.15

*Pilpel, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 2549.

TABLE II*

 β -Naphthylmethyl ether.

Temp.	Molten solid.		$P_{\lambda} = 191.6$	$\mu_{new} \times 10^{18}$
	ϵ	d		
75°	3.588	1.057	387.6	1.12
80°	3.563	1.052	385.5	1.12
85°	3.538	1.048	383.2	1.12
90°	3.514	1.043	381.5	1.12
95°	3.486	1.040	378.7	1.12
100°	3.465	1.035	376.9	1.12

*Present work.

TABLE III*

Temp.	Solvent: benzene.				Solvent: benzene.			
	ϵ_{12} $w_2 = 0.05408$.	d_{12}	P_2	$\mu_{new} \times 10^{18}$	ϵ_{12} $w_2 = 0.1082$.	d_{12}	P_2	$\mu_{new} \times 10^{18}$.
25°	2.347	0.8846	418.4	1.11	2.423	0.6940	425.6	1.13
30°	2.335	0.8789	415.6	1.11	2.412	0.8884	427.1	1.14
35°	2.322	0.8732	406.7	1.10	2.400	0.8828	422.7	1.14
40°	2.309	0.8674	395.0	1.08	2.386	0.8772	418.3	1.14
45°	2.297	0.8618	392.1	1.08	2.374	0.8716	415.4	1.14
	$w_2 = 0.1525$.				$w_2 = 0.1867$.			
25°	2.475	0.9027	412.0	1.10	2.518	0.9082	410.2	1.09
30°	2.462	0.8968	411.0	1.10	2.503	0.9024	407.7	1.09
35°	2.450	0.8908	411.0	1.10	2.489	0.8966	406.0	1.10
40°	2.435	0.8846	405.8	1.11	2.474	0.8908	401.8	1.10
45°	2.423	0.8784	406.8	1.12	2.460	0.8850	399.2	1.10
	$w_2 = 0.2062$.							
25°	2.548	0.9124	412.9	1.10				
30°	2.530	0.9070	408.3	1.09				
35°	2.509	0.9016	399.0	1.08				
40°	2.495	0.8962	295.2	1.08				
45°	2.477	0.8908	398.2	1.10				

* Present work.

TABLE IVA*

*Furan.*Pure liquid. $\mu_{obs} = 0.75$. $P_2 = 74.18$.

Temp.	ϵ	d	P	$\mu_{new} \times 10^{18}$.
25°	2.953	0.9313	142.8	0.61

TABLE IVB*

Solvent: benzene. $\mu_b = 0.71$. Temp. = 25°.

f_2	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	$\mu_{new} \times 10^{18}$.
0.0000	2.276	0.8734		
0.0286	2.289	0.8748	136.3	0.58
0.0608	2.306	0.8763	136.6	0.58
0.0664	2.308	0.8765	135.5	0.58
0.1338	2.340	0.8776	135.1	0.58
0.1355	2.341	0.8787	135.5	0.58
0.1731	2.363	0.8816	137.3	0.59

* Smyth and Walls, *loc. cit.*

TABLE IVc*

Solvent: benzene. $\mu_D = 0.71$. Temp. = 25°.

w_2 .	ϵ_{12} .	d_{12} .	P_2 .	$\mu_{new} \times 10^{18}$.
0.00000	2.2725	0.87378	...	...
0.017095	2.2833	0.87469	139.3	0.60
0.035650	2.2948	0.87562	141.3	0.60
0.037020	2.2956	0.87567	136.0	0.58
0.043975	2.2990	0.87501	140.8	0.60
0.044250	2.3003	0.87596	140.0	0.60
0.056225	2.3077	0.87659	140.5	0.60
0.059350	2.3090	0.87679	138.8	0.59
0.059155	2.3190	0.87678	138.8	0.59
0.079955	2.3209	0.87744	130.6	0.60
0.085105	2.3231	0.87803	139.9	0.60

* Le Fevre, *loc. cit.*

TABLE VA*

Tetrahydrofuran.

Pure liquid. $P_2 = 79.82$.

Temp.	ϵ .	d .	P .	$\mu_{new} \times 10^{18}$.
25°	7.881	0.8838	561.3	1.62
30°	7.762	0.8781	551.1	1.62
35°	7.652	0.8724	549.6	1.63
40°	7.534	0.8664	543.8	1.63
45°	7.422	0.8606	537.9	1.63
50°	7.324	0.8550	533.2	1.63
55°	7.320	0.8492	528.9	1.64

TABLE VB*

Solvent: benzene.

Temp.	ϵ_{12} .	d_{12} .	P_2 .	μ_{new} .	$w_2 = 0.3311$.			μ_{new} .
					ϵ_{12} .	d_{12} .	P_2 .	
					$w_2 = 0.1811$.			
25°	3.114	0.8784	482.0	1.48	3.816	0.8800	484.4	1.48
30°	3.078	0.8740	471.2	1.48	3.766	0.8740	476.8	1.48
35°	3.045	0.8656	466.2	1.47	3.719	0.8680	470.4	1.48
40°	3.010	0.8592	457.8	1.47	3.667	0.862	462.3	1.48
45°	2.976	0.8528	449.4	1.47	3.619	0.8660	455.0	1.48
					$w_2 = 0.5037$.			
25°	4.670	0.8824	491.6	1.50	5.565	0.8828	519.0	1.55
30°	4.602	0.8762	484.9	1.50	5.439	0.8768	507.1	1.54
35°	4.532	0.8700	477.8	1.50	5.313	0.8706	495.1	1.53
40°	4.460	0.8638	470.0	1.49	5.183	0.8646	482.1	1.52
45°	4.391	0.8574	463.1	1.49	5.059	0.8584	470.1	1.51
					$w_2 = 0.8303$.			
25°	6.642	0.8834	533.0	1.57				
30°	6.506	0.8780	523.1	1.57				
35°	6.372	0.8724	512.3	1.56				
40°	6.232	0.8666	502.9	1.55				
45°	6.098	0.8612	492.6	1.55				

* Present work.

TABLE VC*

(a). Solvent : benzene at 25°.					(b). Solvent : benzene at 50°.			
f_2	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}
0.00000	2.2755	0.8733	...	...	2.2255	0.8464	...	...
0.00870	2.314	0.8737	494.3	1.50	2.258	0.8467	436.8	1.48
0.00888	2.315	0.8737	506.7	1.52	2.259	0.8468	439.2	1.46
0.01040	2.266	0.8737	509.7	1.53	2.266	0.8468	452.0	1.48
0.01770	2.296	0.8739	525.4	1.56	2.266	0.8471	477.4	1.49
0.01887	2.307	0.8739	525.9	1.56	2.303	0.8472	466.3	1.51
(c). Solvent : dioxane at 25°.					(d). Solvent : dioxane at 50°.			
0.00000	2.261	1.0312	...	...	2.214	1.0027	...	...
0.01778	2.347	1.0314	506.0	1.52	2.201	1.0028	472.4	1.52
0.01898	2.352	1.0313	505.8	1.52	2.296	1.0027	463.6	1.50
0.03259	2.419	1.0295	505.3	1.52	2.355	1.0010	472.5	1.52
0.05522	2.533	1.0264	618.0	1.54	2.454	0.9978	479.8	1.51
0.07886	2.660	1.0230	528.9	1.56	2.569	0.9944	492.3	1.56

* Smyth and Walls, *loc. cit.*

TABLE VI*

(a) <i>o</i> -Dimethoxybenzene.					(b) <i>m</i> -Dimethoxybenzene.			
Pure liquid. $P_2 = 167.4$.					Pure liquid. $P_2 = 166.2$.			
Temp.	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}
25°	4.213	1.0824	410.5	1.15	5.363	1.0650	566.3	1.48
35°	4.189	1.0712	412.5	1.17	5.234	1.0538	553.2	1.48
45°	4.64	1.0602	412.7	1.19	5.100	1.0426	543.4	1.48
55°	4.161	1.0400	416.5	1.22	4.996	1.0314	535.8	1.49
65°	4.159	1.0380	420.7	1.25	4.889	1.0202	527.0	1.49
75°	4.153	1.0268	429.3	1.28	4.780	1.0090	518.0	1.50
85°	4.150	1.0158	428.5	1.31	4.677	0.9978	509.4	1.50

* Present work.

TABLE VII*

p-Dimethoxybenzene.

Molten liquid. $P_2 = 163.6$.				
Temp.	ϵ	d	P	μ_{new}
56°	5.37.5	1.0250	589.5	1.60
77°	5.1385	1.0140	563.9	1.60
98°	4.9414	1.0023	543.3	1.60
121°	4.6936	0.9880	516.5	1.59

* Miss Kulkarni, Ph. D. thesis, Bombay University.

TABLE VIII*
Pentachloroethane.
Pure liquid. $P_2 = 151.7$.

Temp.	ϵ .	d .	P.	μ_{new} .
25°	3.716	1.672	328.6	0.98
35°	3.616	1.657	319.4	0.97
45°	3.505	1.643	308.4	0.95
55°	3.416	1.628	300.2	0.94
65°	3.332	1.613	292.5	0.93
75°	3.242	1.599	283.6	0.91
85°	3.158	1.584	275.5	0.90

TABLE IX*
Vanillin.

Solvent: benzene. $P_2 = 161.8$.

Temp.	ϵ_{12} .	d_{12} .	P_{12} .	μ_{new} .	ϵ_{12} .	d_{12} .	P_{12} .	μ_{new} .	ϵ_{12} .	d_{12} .	P_{12} .	μ_{new} .
	$w_2 = 0.02757$.			$w_2 = 0.04245$.				$w_2 = 0.0644$.				
25°	2.452	0.8808	1263	2.45	2.590	0.8871	1260	2.45	2.641	0.8890	1264	2.45
30°	2.436	0.8750	1247	2.45	2.574	0.8811	1256	2.46	2.623	0.8836	1247	2.45
35°	2.422	0.8692	1225	2.44	2.559	0.8750	1249	2.47	2.607	0.8782	1237	2.46
40°	2.408	0.8632	1207	2.44	2.541	0.8690	1227	2.47	2.590	0.8728	1215	2.45
45°	2.394	0.8574	1197	2.45	2.524	0.8630	1215	2.47	2.572	0.8674	1196	2.45

* Present work.

TABLE X
Moments.

Compound.	Solvent.	μ_{new} .	μ_{DCM} .	μ_{Oms} .	μ_{Eth} .	μ_{Calc} .
Phenetole	Vapour ¹	...	1.76	...	...	1.14
	Liquid ² (20°)	1.15	...	1.29	1.40	...
	C_6H_6 ³	1.15	...	...	...	...
	CCl_4 ³	1.15	...	...	...	...
β -Naphthylmethyl ether	Molten liquid ³ (75-100°)	1.12	...	1.19	1.37	1.14
	Benzene ³	1.14	...	...	...	...
Tetrahydrofuran	Liquid ³ (22-55°)	1.63	...	1.86	1.89	1.48
	Benzene ³	1.55	...	...	...	...
	"	1.52	1.71	...	...	...
	Dioxane ⁴	1.52	1.81	...	...	...
o-Dimethoxybenzene	Liquid ³ (25-85°)	1.15-1.31	...	1.28	1.39	2.02(I)
	Liquid ³ (25-85°)	1.49	...	1.48	1.60	1.05(II)
m- " "	"	"	"	1.65	1.75	1.05(I) 2.02(II)
p- " "	Liquid ³ (56-121°)	1.60	...	1.79	1.8	1.989(I) 0.0(II)
Pentachloroethane	Liquid ³ (25°-85°)	0.94	...	1.09	1.23	0.99
Vanillin	Benzene ¹	2.45	...	...	...	2.35
	Benzene ⁴	3.00	3.0	...	...	...
Furan	Vapour ⁷	...	1.5kT.	...	...	...
	Liquid ¹⁴ (25°)	0.75	0.72	0.75	0.82	0.74
	Benzene ⁴	0.71	0.71	...	...	...
	Benzene ⁷	0.74	0.71	...	...	...

1. Landolt-Bornstein, 'Table of Moments.
2. Filpel, *loc. cit.*
3. Present work.
4. Smyth and Walls, *loc. cit.*

5. Miss Kulkarni, *loc. cit.*
6. Shott-L'vova *et al.*, *loc. cit.*
7. LeFevre *et al.*, *loc. cit.*

DISCUSSION

It has already been shown by us (*loc. cit.*) that the moment of the C-O-C group in ethers is 1.14.

Phenetole.—The recalculation by the new equation of the data of Pilpel for phenetole in pure liquid state and in benzene and carbon tetrachloride solutions provides a value of 1.15 in all the three cases. The Onsager and the Kirkwood values for pure liquid are 1.29 and 1.40 respectively. The vapour value is 1.16.

The moment of the C-O-C group is 1.14 which is also the molecular moment. This value compares with the value in the vapour state and also with the new values in the liquid state and in solutions.

β -Naphthylmethyl Ether.—The new moment of β -naphthylmethyl ether in molten state and in solution is 1.12 which is independent of temperature and concentration. The Onsager and the Kirkwood moments in liquid state are 1.19 and 1.37 respectively.

C-O (1) and C-O (2) are each reduced to a moment of 0.99 because of mutual induction. The resultant of the two is 1.14, which is also the molecular moment. This value is in good agreement with the moment of 1.12 in molten state and 1.10 in benzene solution.

Furan.—Recalculation of the data of Smyth and Walls (*loc. cit.*) and of LeFevre *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) by the new equation provides moment values of 0.58 and 0.60 respectively. The vapour moment as given by LeFevre *et al.* is 0.72. It appears that in pure liquid state and in solution there is a decrease in hindered rotation which increases $2j+1=2(1kT)$ to $2j+1=3(1.5kT)$ whereby the moment is increased to a value of 0.74. The Onsager and the Kirkwood moments for liquid furan are 0.75 and 0.82 respectively.

Each of C-O (1) and C-O (2) is reduced to a moment of 0.74 because of mutual induction. The resultant of the two, which is also the molecular moment, is 0.74. This value compares well with the vapour value of 0.72 and the value in pure liquid state and in solution, when $2j+1=3(1.5kT)$.

Tetrahydrofuran.—The new moment of tetrahydrofuran in pure liquid state is 1.63, which is independent of temperature. The new moment in benzene solution

is independent of temperature, but varies slightly with concentration. The recalculation by the new equation of the data of Smyth and Walls (*loc. cit.*) for tetrahydrofuran in benzene and in dioxane furnishes 1.52 as the value for the molecular moment. The Onsager and the Kirkwood values for the molecule in liquid state are 1.86 and 1.89 respectively.

The calculated value is 1.48, which compares with the new value both in the liquid state and in solution.

o-Dimethoxybenzene.—The new moment of *o*-dimethoxybenzene in pure liquid state varies with temperature. The values are 1.15 at 25° and 1.31 at 85°. The corresponding values by the Onsager and the Kirkwood equations are 1.28-1.48 and 1.39-1.60 respectively.

(I)

(II)

The moment of the C-O-C group is 1.14. The resultant moment of the molecule is given by the resultant of the moments of the two C-O-C groups. The value calculated is 2.02 for structure (I) and 1.05 for structure (II). It appears that at low temperature structure (II) predominates, while with increase of temperature structure (I) begins to contribute appreciably.

m-Dimethoxybenzene.—The new moment of *m*-dimethoxybenzene in pure liquid state is 1.40, which is independent of temperature. The corresponding values given by the Onsager and the Kirkwood equations are 1.65 and 1.75 respectively.

(I)

(II)

The moment of the C-O-C group is 1.14. The moment calculated for structure (I) is 1.05 while that calculated for structure (II) is 2.02. The mean of the two is 1.53, which compares with the new moment in the liquid state. Both the structures are possible as there is no steric hindrance.

p-Dimethoxybenzene.—The moment of *p*-dimethoxybenzene in the liquid state, as obtained by the application of the new equation, is 1.60 and is independent of temperature. The Onsager and the Kirkwood moments are 1.79 and 1.89 respectively.

The moment of C-O(1) cancels that of C-O(3). The moment for the molecule is given by the resultant of the moments of C-O(2) and C-O(4). The moment calculated for structure (I) is 1.98 and that calculated for (II) is zero. It appears that structure (I) predominates, but there is a small contribution from structure (II).

Pentachloroethane.—The dipole moment of pentachloroethane in pure liquid state has been measured for the first time. The new moment is 0.94, which is practically independent of temperature. The Onsager and the Kirkwood values are 1.09 and 1.23 respectively.

The C-Cl bond (I) and C-Cl bond (II) cancel C-Cl bond (IV) and C-Cl bond (V) respectively. Because of induction from the C-Cl bonds (I, II, IV & V) the C-Cl bond (III) is reduced to 1/3 its original value. The effective moment of C-Cl bond (III) is 0.57. This together with the moment of 0.42 for the C-H bond gives a resultant moment of 0.99, which is the molecular moment. This compares with the new moment observed in the pure liquid state. The Onsager and the Kirkwood values are higher.

Vanillin

The new moments of vanillin in benzene solution is 2.45, which is independent of temperature and concentration.

The resultant moment of the C—O(I) and C—O(II) is 1.14. The moment of C—O(III) is 1.48. The other moments are C=O equal to 2.90 and OH=2.40.

Structure (I).—The moment along C_4-C_5 is 2.4, that along C_3-C_4 is 2.9 and that along C—O(III) is 2.62. The resultant of the moments along C_4-C_5 and C_3-C_4 is 2.685 which together with the moment along C—O(III) gives the molecular moment, the value of which is 0.42.

Structure (II).—The resultant of the moment 2.9 along C_3-C_4 and 2.62 along C—O (III) is 2.77. This adds on vectorially to the moment 2.4 along C_4-C_5 and yields a value of 5.16 for the molecular moment.

Structure (III).—The resultant of the moments 2.4 along C_4-C_5 and 2.9 along C_3-C_4 is 2.685. This vectorially adds up to the moment 0.34 along C—O (III) and gives a value of 2.35 for the molecular moment.

Structure (IV).—The moment 2.4 along C_4-C_5 adds on vectorially to the resultant (2.75) of 2.9 along C_3-C_4 and 0.34 along C—O (III) and gives the molecular moment, the value of which is 5.14.

The moments of structure (III) and (IV) are very high and that of structure (I) is very low. The observed moment of 2.45 indicates that the moment is entirely represented by structure (III). The moment calculated for this structure is 2.35.

The detailed results are summarised in the tables. The moment values of different ethers obtained by the D.C.M., the Onsager, the Kirkwood and the new equations are summarised in the table of moments. It will be seen that the new values of moments in liquids and solutions compare well with the vapour values as well as with the values calculated theoretically. The values of moments in liquid state, as given by the Onsager and the Kirkwood equations, are consistently higher.